

Synergistic Effects and Molecular Mechanism of Metformin and Vildagliptin in experimental Prediabetes

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Abstract:

Background: Prediabetes, a transitional state preceding type 2 diabetes, is linked to heightened risks of cardiovascular events and stroke. While insulin resistance is well established as a primary feature, recent insights emphasize the involvement of beta cell dysfunction in Prediabetes.

Objective: This study explores the combined therapeutic impact of Metformin and the DPP4 inhibitor: Vildagliptin in addressing both insulin resistance and beta cell regeneration in a rat model of prediabetes and elucidates the molecular mode of action.

Methods: Adult male rats were subjected to a high-fat diet followed by a high-fat, high-sugar liquid regimen to induce Prediabetic conditions. Subsequent assessments included biochemical parameters, histopathological studies.

Results: The combination therapy of Metformin and Vildagliptin resulted in better glycemic control than Metformin& Vildagliptin alone.

Conclusion: Co-administration of Metformin and Vildagliptin offers a dual-targeted approach by improving both insulin sensitivity and beta cell function, showing enhanced therapeutic potential over Metformin monotherapy for Prediabetes management.

Key Words: Metformin, DPP4 inhibitors, Beta cell function, Prediabetes

Introduction:

Prediabetes is a metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels that remain below the threshold for diabetes but significantly increase the risk of developing Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), cardiovascular diseases, and stroke^[1]. If left unaddressed, it progresses due to beta-cell dysfunction and insulin resistance. However, research suggests that modifications in lifestyle, diet, and pharmacological treatments can effectively manage or even reverse the condition^[2]. Beta cells in the pancreas, which are responsible for insulin secretion and glucose regulation, become overworked in Prediabetes, resulting in reduced insulin production and impaired glycemic control. As the condition advances, beta-cell function deteriorates further, leading to worsening insulin resistance and persistent hyperglycemia^[3]. While pharmaceutical interventions aim to enhance insulin secretion by improving beta-cell function, there remains debate about whether stimulating exhausted beta cells is more beneficial than reducing their strain.

Metformin continues to be a widely used treatment for prediabetes and T2DM, primarily targeting insulin resistance by inhibiting hepatic glucose production and improving glucose absorption^[4]. Additionally, it exhibits anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects that help preserve beta-cell function, though its direct role in beta-cell regeneration is limited. In contrast, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, such as Sitagliptin, have demonstrated the ability to protect beta cells and stimulate their growth. These inhibitors prevent the breakdown of glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), a hormone essential for insulin secretion and beta-cell survival. By maintaining GLP-1 levels, DPP-4 inhibitors promote beta-cell proliferation while reducing apoptosis, potentially offering long-term benefits in managing prediabetes^[3].

Recent studies indicate that combining metformin with DPP-4 inhibitors may produce synergistic effects in Prediabetes treatment. While metformin focuses on insulin resistance, DPP-4 inhibitors emphasize beta-cell preservation and regeneration. Together, these therapies may help slow or even prevent the progression from Prediabetes to T2DM by addressing both beta-cell dysfunction and insulin resistance. The comparative effects of metformin and DPP-4 inhibitors will highlight their potential complementary roles in managing Prediabetes. Metformin remains fundamental due to its insulin-sensitizing properties, whereas DPP-4 inhibitors may show promise in sustaining beta-cell function and promoting regeneration. A combination therapy may enhance long-term glycemic control by tackling the underlying mechanisms contributing to disease progression. Further research is needed to generate data to assess the efficacy and the molecular mechanism of this therapeutic approach.

Materials & Methods:

Experimental Animal - The study utilized adult male Wistar rats aged 4–6 weeks, weighing 100–120 g, housed in the Central Animal Facility at MGM Medical College, Navi Mumbai, India. The rats were maintained under standard laboratory conditions in compliance with ethical guidelines established by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, adhering to the Guidelines for the Use and Care of Experimental Animals in Research, along with regulations from the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals and the Indian National Science Academy. They were housed in air-conditioned rooms with a natural light-dark cycle in polyacrylic cages measuring 38 × 23 × 15 cm, with a maximum of four rats per cage. The animals were provided ad libitum access to either a standard diet or a high-fat diet (HFD) along with 25% dextrose water.

Experimental Model for Prediabetes: For the experimental model of prediabetes, male Wistar rats with an average body weight of 100–120 g were fed a commercially available high-fat, high-carbohydrate diet for 9 weeks. The diet composition included moisture, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, nitrogen-free extract (NFE), calcium, and phosphorus. Additionally, 25% dextrose was provided in drinking bottles, and a liquid high-fat diet suspension—prepared using vanaspati ghee and coconut oil in a 3:1 ratio—was administered via oral feeding (3 mL/kg) for 9 weeks to induce prediabetes. Weekly blood glucose assessments ensured that levels remained within the prediabetic range (100–125 mg/dL). After the study, the rats underwent biochemical, & histopathological analysis to evaluate the effects of the experimental intervention.

The experimental rats were randomly assigned to three groups, with twelve rats in each group for comparative analysis.

Experimental Groups

1. **Normal Control** — Animals received standard pellet diet and purified water for 24 h ad libitum and were considered as the normal control (NC) group.
2. **Disease Control** — Animals received a commercially available high-fat high-carbohydrate diet, 25% dextrose water in bottles for 24 h, and 3 ml/kg liquid fat solution (Vanaspati ghee and coconut oil in the ratio of 3:1 [v/v]) each day over 9 weeks and were considered as the Disease Control (DC) group.
3. **Metformin** -- Animals receiving a commercially available high-fat high-carbohydrate diet, 25% dextrose in bottles for 24 h, and 3 ml/kg liquid fat solution (Vanaspati ghee and coconut oil in the ratio of 3:1 [v/v]) each day for 9 weeks. Subsequently, after confirming Prediabetes at the 3rd week, Metformin (100 mg/kg) was additionally administered orally to the experimental rats till the end of the experimental duration.

4. **Vildagliptin** — Animals receiving a commercially available high-fat high-carbohydrate diet, 25% dextrose in bottles for 24 h and 3 ml/kg liquid fat solution (Vanaspati ghee and coconut oil in the ratio of 3:1 [v/v]) each day over 9 weeks. Subsequently, after confirming Prediabetes at the 3rd week, vildagliptin (10 mg/kg) was additionally administered orally to the experimental rats till the end of the experimental duration.
5. **Vildagliptin + Metformin** -- Animals receiving a commercially available high-fat high-carbohydrate diet, 25% dextrose in bottles for 24 h and 3 ml/kg liquid fat solution (Vanaspati ghee and coconut oil in the ratio of 3:1 [v/v]) each day over 9 weeks. Subsequently, after confirming Prediabetes at the 3rd week, Vildagliptin +Metformin (100 mg/kg + 10 mg/kg) was additionally administered orally to the experimental rats till the end of the experimental duration.

Evaluation Parameters

1) Assessment of body weight changes and mortality, if any

The animals' body weights (gm) were noted at the beginning of the study and then weekly until the end of the study period. At the same time, any deaths that occurred throughout the oral administration period for the corresponding groups were also recorded.

2) Efficacy of Metformin and Vildagliptin Combination in Prediabetes

A) Estimation of Biochemical Parameters

At the end of the study, heart puncture technique was used to obtain rat blood samples from all experimental groups under light ketamine anaesthesia (40 mg/kg) to estimate the biochemical parameters: Blood glucose, Glycated hemoglobin (HBA1c), Serum Insulin, C-peptide, CPK MB (Creatinine phosphokinase), and Lipid Profile.

B) Histopathological Assessment

At the end of the study, experimental animals were sacrificed, and organs were excised immediately and rinsed with ice-cold saline and trimmed off with their respective connective tissue and fat. All the organs were instantly fixed in 10% buffered formalin solution and weighed. Cross sections (5 μ m thick) of the fixed myocardial tissues were cut. These sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and visualized under a light microscope. The investigators performing the histopathologic evaluation were blind to biochemical results.

3) Mechanisms of Metformin and Vildagliptin Combination in Prediabetes

A) Insulin Resistance and Beta Cell Function:

- **HOMA-IR** - Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance
 - **Formula:** $\text{Glucose (mmol/L)} \times \text{Insulin (mU/L)} / 22.5$
- **HOMA β** - Homeostatic Model Assessment for beta cell function
 - **Formula:** $20 \times \text{Insulin (mU/L)} / \text{Glucose (mmol/L)} - 3.5$

Ethical Approval: -Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) obtained (**Approval No: 2023/10/03**)

Animal sacrifices method: Cardiac puncture technique was used to obtain rat blood samples from all experimental groups under light ketamine anesthesia (40 mg/kg).

Results:

1) Assessment of body weight changes:

Body Weight: The DC group showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in body weight every week as compared with the NC group rats. The decrease in body weight of the DC group rats was sustained at the end of the 9th week. In the Metformin-treated group, there was significant weight loss as compared to DC at the 9th week. In the Vildagliptin monotherapy & Vildagliptin +Metformin treated group, there was a significant increase in weight as compared to DC at 9th weeks

2) Efficacy of Metformin and Vildagliptin Combination in Prediabetes

A. Efficacy in Prediabetes

a) Diabetic Parameters:

- i. **Fasting Blood glucose** values above 100 mg/dl confirmed the induction of Prediabetes. The blood glucose levels in the DC group rats were significantly higher than compared of the NC group rats at 8 weeks. Prediabetes was confirmed at the 3rd week after the induction protocol. Metformin, Vildagliptin, and the monotherapy-treated group show a significant decrease in fasting blood sugar at 9th weeks as compared to DC. The most significant decrease in fasting blood sugar was seen in the Vildagliptin + Metformin-treated groups at the 9th week as compared to DC (**Fig. 1**).

Figure 1: Change in Fasting Blood Glucose in the various experimental group

Figure 2: Change in HbA1c in the various experimental groups

ii. **HbA1c** also increased significantly in the DC group as compared to the NC, confirming Prediabetes (**Fig. 2**). Metformin, Vildagliptin, and Vildagliptin +Metformin treatment demonstrated significant antidiabetic effects as indicated by a significant decrease in blood glucose ($p < 0.001$) and HbA1c ($p < 0.01$) (**Fig. 2**). The most significant reduction in HbA1C was observed with Vildagliptin +Metformin group as compared to DC control.

- iii. **Insulin & C-Peptide:** Serum Insulin and C-Peptide increased in the DC group, which was reduced after Metformin, Vildagliptin treatment. Results were most statistically significant for reduction in Insulin and C- Peptide with Vildagliptin +Metformin group as compared to DC control (**Table 1**)

Table No. 1:Change in Insulin, C-Peptide, HOMA IR & HOMA β in the various experimental groups

	Normal Control	Disease Control	Metformin	Vildagliptin	Vildagliptin + metformin
INSULIN	0.25 ± 0.024	0.433 ± 0.487	0.16 ± 0.06	0.32 ± 0.13	0.29 ± 0.12
C PEPTIDE	0.013 ± 0.001	0.01 ± 0.004	0.01 ± 0.03	0.02 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.001
HOMA IR	0.04 ± 0.004	0.11 ± 0.14	0.06 ± 0.008	0.86 ± 0.015	0.05 ± 0.03
HOMA β	11.49 ± 5.19	0.69 ± 0.29**	0.4 ± 0.084	0.81 ± 0.05#	0.96 ± 0.04#

HOMA-IR - Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance; **HOMA β** - Homeostatic Model Assessment for beta cell function, **p < 0.01 , #p < 0.01 Vs DC

b. Histopathological Changes in Prediabetes

- **Histopathology of the Pancreas:** The pancreas of the NC group rats was characterized by an organized pattern and showed normal architecture of islets of Langerhans and the beta cells (**Fig. 3A**). The DC group showed damaged islets of Langerhans, atrophy of

beta cells and reduced beta cell mass (**Fig. 3B**). In the Metformin-treated group, there was less inflammation and edema (**Fig 3C**). In the vildagliptin group, rats show less inflammation (**Fig. 3D**), and in the Vildagliptin +Metformin shows very less edema (**Fig. 3E**).

Discussion:

In Prediabetes, the beta cell is stressed out, resulting in insufficient insulin production and glycemic control. Type 2 diabetes develops as the function of the beta cell declines. As the disease advances, the insulin response decreases, and glucose levels rise. Earlier studies concentrated on Insulin resistance (IR), which has been identified as an essential factor in Prediabetes towards type 2 diabetes progression. However, more recent pharmaceutical approaches aim to increase beta-cell function by preserving beta-cell mass. Preserving beta cell function in prediabetes is crucial because it can significantly delay—or even prevent—the progression to type 2 diabetes. Therefore, targeting both beta cell dysfunction and peripheral insulin resistance is critical for effective treatment of Prediabetes. ^[3]

Metformin, which targets IR, is the only recommended antidiabetic for the current pharmacotherapy of Prediabetes. Over the past few years, a reliable method to improve beta cell

function has been to increase insulin release in a glucose-dependent way by stimulating the action of incretin peptides. GLP-1 receptor agonists are excellent at promoting biphasic insulin release. They also rarely induce hypoglycaemia or weight gain, which is a step forward in treating type 2 diabetes. DPP-4 inhibitors can improve beta-cell function by extending the half-life of incretins like GLP-1. This has led to improved delivery of GLP-1/glucagon-derived peptides.^[3]

Research findings indicate that the antidiabetic drugs, DPP-4 inhibitors, can improve beta-cell functioning and also increase beta-cell mass. As a result, a combination of Metformin and DPP-4 inhibitors may be effective in treating Prediabetes by improving beta-cell function and insulin resistance. This study also determined that DPP-4 inhibitors can stimulate beta cell regeneration, resulting in new insulin-producing cells. This would revolutionize the management of Prediabetes and could be a promising therapeutic option to halt or delay disease development.

In the present study, Prediabetes was successfully established as indicated by an increase in fasting Blood Sugar, glycated haemoglobin, plasma Insulin, and C-peptide in the Prediabetic Disease Control group rats when compared to the Normal Control group. Similar results were seen in a study done by Luciano Rossetti et al^[5], Mengsiyu Li et al^[6], SIWEI ZHANG et al^[7], and R. Yanardag et al^[8]. Metformin, the conventional treatment, reduced Fasting Blood Sugar, Glycated Haemoglobin, Plasma Insulin, and C-peptide levels. These findings were similar to those reported by Luciano Rossetti et al^[5], Mengsiyu Li et al^[6], SIWEI ZHANG et al^[7]. Therefore, this experimental model of Prediabetes was used to study the efficacy of Metformin, Vildagliptin monotherapy, and Metformin and Vildagliptin combination therapy.

Vildagliptin (DPP 4 inhibitor) also showed a decrease in fasting blood sugar, glycated haemoglobin, plasma insulin, and C peptide. This study were comparable with the results presented by Nattayaporn Apaijai et al ^[9]. In monotherapy, the most significant results were seen with Vildagliptin (DPP 4 inhibitor) as compared to the conventional treatment metformin. The combination group Vildagliptin +Metformin demonstrated the most significant effects, with lower levels of fasting blood sugar, glycated haemoglobin, plasma insulin, & C peptide.

Efficacy of Metformin, Vildagliptin, and Vildagliptin + Metformin was also determined using histopathological alterations of the pancreas to evaluate ultrastructure changes. Histopathological examination of the pancreas reveals that there is reduced damage in the treated group compared to the Prediabetes and, thus supporting the biochemical findings.

Conclusion:

This study provides novel insights into the combined effects of Metformin and Vildagliptin in a Prediabetic model, demonstrating their ability to improve both insulin sensitivity and beta-cell functionality.

Declaration:

Competing Interests: No competing Interests.

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